

INDIAN ECONOMY AND THE CHALLENGES AHEAD

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Abstract

Globalisation per se is not a problem; in fact it is bringing opportunities for learning about organisation, coordination and management of available human capital, scarce resources and technology to increase production and productivity. This globalisation has progressed in tandem with economic growth during the period of Narsimha Rao and Atal Bihari Vajpayee. The 1990s policy reforms consisted of three major elements viz., domestic decontrol, tax reforms and external opening, and one smaller element – public sector investment. These reforms succeeded in promoting competition and raising growth rate of India's economy, resulting in reducing gap between the India's per capita income and the world average. Indian industry especially corporate sector has benefited a lot from globalisation. Now, in order to survive in the era of globalisation we have to carry forward and complete the reforms in agriculture decontrol, simplification of taxes, de-monopolisation of infrastructure enterprises, labour laws and land market reforms.

Key Words: Globalisation, Economy, Challenges, domestic decontrol.

Prologue

Have you ever wondered why ancient India was called *Sone ki chidiya* (The golden bird). The answer lies in Angus Maddison's historical tracking of world's GDP. India was world's largest economy in I AD with China (Sabharwal, 2008) as number two. According to the calculations by Angus Maddison, from at least the beginning of the common era until the early nineteenth

century, China and India accounted for around half of the global GDP. Both the countries were very well knit with the rest of the globe but both economies went downhill between the early 18th century and the late 20th century. The decline can be attributed to a multitude of factors and events: the industrial revolution in Europe; the formation and expansion of the United States of America; China had to jostle social unrest and various other social issues under Mao Zedong; China's decline during the Ming and Quing dynasities; the impact of British rule on India in the 20th century. At the time of the arrival of the British, Indian economy was by and large self-sufficient, possessing of a fine balance between agriculture and industry. The British came to India as merchants in the middle of the 17th century, not to rule but to trade. The initial contact that India had with Britain was not crown but with one of the earliest multinational corporations of the world, the East India Company. Commercial interest was merged with the political interest. They gained political supremacy around the middle of the 18th century. Henceforth, the Indian would be relieved of their resources not just through asymmetric trade and exchange but also taxation and state sponsored extortion. The fear of multinationals and a mistrust of business and trade would get etched in the collective memory of India. Independent India would design its economic policy in the shadow of this memory.

Economic Strategy after Independence

India followed mixed economy approach to economic development, based on what came to be called the Mahalanobis-Nehru strategy (Attar,1990) of development. A mixed economy applies a fair balance between social goals and individual goals. It implies the concerted or harmonious organisation of the public and the private sectors. The sectors have to be so reorganised as to become mutually reinforcing rather than mutually obstructive. Similarly, planning arrangement and market arrangements are so adjusted that each is used for the social goals to which it is most suited and yet the two mechanisms are not permitted to become mutually contradictory. Further, a social democratic mixed economy implies a balanced commitment to freedom, to equality and material progress. The logic behind this approach was that the industry, which were critically important for the economy such as coal mining, steel, power and roads should be retained by the government. The private sector was allowed to establish industries and business enterprises but was subject to control and regulation that came in the form of laws. It leads to the creation of

large bureaucracy to control and monitor business and set-up barriers to foreign goods and investment. The tariff on import was rose steadily, as successive finance ministers fell over one another to demonstrate their resolve not to allow foreigners to exploit Indians.

India followed an inward-looking and import substitution strategy of economic development during 1950-1980. Beginning 1980s policy makers started realising the drawbacks of this policy, which inhibited competitiveness and efficiency, produced a much lower rate of growth than expected and led to inferior quality of domestic production with high cost as compared to world prices. By mid 1980s it was clear that drastic shift in policy was needed to speed up the rate of growth. It was also found that the several laws and institutional features, which were created to regulate and run the private sector smoothly, had become a major hindrance to its development. We had arrived at a severe financial crunch. This financial crunch forced the government to borrow money from international financial institutions. All these led to framing of a New Economic Policy (Pant, 2003). Under the new economic policy, license, quota and permit are replaced by three new strategies, which are called liberalisation, privatisation and globalisation. After assuming power at the centre, the government of Prime Minister Rajeev Gandhi introduced a series of measures to reduce control on industries, particularly large industries. The process of economic reforms initiated in 1985 got a boost when the government of Prime Minister Narsimha Rao announced a new industrial policy in the Indian Parliament on July 24, 1991, which has already proved a watershed in the post-independence history of India.

From the late 1980s world started changing very rapidly. Before capitalism, societies were reproduced via ‘relations of personal dependence’ like kinship, serfdom, feudal obligations, etc. It is only in capitalism that a new form of social connectedness emerges, where social reproduction no longer relies on relations of direct personal dependence but where “dependence is mediated by things” or commodities. It was a period of critical times in international relations. It was the time when the super power rivalry got almost eliminated. The end of cold war politics following the disintegration and collapse of Soviet Union and restructure of Eastern European countries and weakening of communism as an ideological force in international politics have changed both the ideological and procedural aspects of international relations, which have paved a way for the emergence of a new global economic order characterised by globalisation. The dynamic of globalisation has thrown a whole range of new problems for the non-aligned developing countries. Nehru formulated India’s non-aligned strategy, which became a movement

of solidarity and co-operation among the newly liberated countries of Asia, Africa and Latin America. Non-alignment movement (NAM) was thus formulated as a solidarity movement for giving voice to what is known as Third World Countries or Developing Countries. The principles of non-alignment are defined in the Bandung (Indonesia) Declaration of 1955 (Narang, 2003) and reiterated in Brioni (Yugoslavia) Declaration of 1955 by Nehru, Tito of Yugoslavia and Nasser of Egypt. The basic thrust of the movement is in favour of peace, disarmament, development, independence, eradication of poverty and illiteracy.

New Economic Policy and Challenges of Globalisation

After new economic policy 1991, the world has changed a lot. We are now a part of the new global economic order. The thrust of the new world economic order is on market oriented policies. New developments in the field of communication, rising debts, declining and aspiring for higher growth in developing countries have helped developed countries to put pressure on these countries through international bodies like World Bank and IMF to integrate their economies with the market oriented world economy, make structural adjustments to accommodate the interest of the multinational company and liberalize their own economies. The process, which is bringing the world closer everyday, is commonly referred to as globalisation. India began responding to globalisation from early 1980s by warmly welcoming the technological developments. It was in the wake of the external repayment liability crisis of 1991 that government took a qualitative turn towards liberalisation. It involve the major changes in policy i.e., trade policy reform, industrial policy reform, exchange rate policy reform, capital market reform and financial reform.

In the context of globalisation, the above mentioned liberalisation means freedom of trade and investment, removal of government control on allocation of resources in the domestic economy facilitating market forces to determine its courses and directions. Liberalisation and globalisation has increased the scale and allocative efficiency of markets for goods and capital. It has created global electronic communication system, spread of information technology, growth of global capital markets and the greater flow of short –term speculative capital, foreign direct investment by multinational corporations, and movement of people across borders. These, in turn, have also led to the rise of social movements such as of women, peasants, ethnic communities and displaced people etc., thereby mobilising more people (Nauriyal et.al, 2009). In the cultural field,

globalisation has helped in the global circulation of cultural goods. Globalisation has helped in the expansion of global market and capital flow, tourism and travel services, banking and insurance, entertainment and media services. Unlike primary sector, secondary sector and tertiary sector have got more attention in the process of globalisation. The exogenous technique of liberalisation and globalisation has accelerated the growth rate of the Indian economy from what Professor Raj Krishna called as 'Hindu' growth rate (1.5 per cent per annum) to high-tech and multinational-led high growth rate. This high growth rate is not only restricted to manufacturing and tertiary sector but also little attention is paid to the primary sector, labour standard, poverty reduction and human rights. In the present contest of globalisation, associated with trade and financial liberalisation, the contribution of information and communication technology to gross domestic production (GDP) growth is rising sharply and becoming the driving force behind rising inequalities, as it raises the demand for skills that are in short supply and it has greatly highly unequally distributed between different regions, income groups, and between males and females. Moreover, competitive markets may be the best guarantee of efficiency, but not necessarily of equity. Globalisation has been verified for increasing poverty and inequalities in the distribution of resources in the society. It has divided the country in two parts what is called *India* and another one is called *Bharat*. *India* comprises white-collar jobs, bureaucrats, industrialists, corporate, and rich men and women while *Bharat* comprises poor people, labour class, dalits, and tribal etc. In order to sustain in the era of globalisation, high growth associated with trade and financial liberalisation must percolate to these (*Bharat*) people. It has greatly circumscribed the power of nation-state under pressure from multinational companies. Multinational Corporation is successfully promoting consumerism and western values. The undermining of social sciences and humanities is already having detrimental effects on society. The issue of whether globalisation will be able to fulfil the aspirations of the common people of the developing countries is to be handled by each country in their own way. Since globalisation is a reality, which cannot be wished away, the discussion on the merits and demerits of globalisation has now been replaced by discussion on the measures, which can help the country derive more advantages from globalisation and minimise its disadvantages. We must be aware that there are no panaceas in economic policy. We have to commensurate the advantage of globalisation with the basic objective of our planning like eradication of poverty, unemployment, and improvement in living standards of people. This is precisely where development, an issue

larger than growth encompassing social, political and cultural dimensions, assumes critical importance (Bashu, 2001). Globalisation, therefore, has to be looked at in the context of both higher economic growth as well as panacea for bridging the gap between haves and have not. The challenge for the developing countries is in giving a decent and dignified existence to their poorer sections. Does globalisation has the ability to serve this purpose? It certainly does. But its success in reducing poverty would depend upon how an individual country approaches the issue of globalisation. We have to prepare for flexibility. Developing countries lack flexibilities that residents of developed countries take for granted. To stick with one policy, unbendingly, is to make the same mistake of policy stubbornness that led India to her predicament.

In the era of globalisation, it is not enough to have knowledge of information technology, engineering etc. If the nation does not have organisation to share and exchange this knowledge and to harness it, where it is needed, it will be a miserable and poor nation. A society of high human capital and poor organisation is like a society where lot of people have computer but there is no internet to link up information in these computers. We must rethink our notions of 'good governance' and 'good government.' Government and governance are not synonymous. New modes of good governance that do not require an overbearing government are necessary, not just for India but also for the world. We need systems of governance that enable better coordination, not control. To survive under new global economic order huge public and private investment in research and development are required. Investment in human resource development, protection of copy rights; intellectual property rights; patents can provide the incentive for research, creativity, and innovation. Government's regulatory environment must be conducive to business. It is a matter of shame that "Doing Business Report 2008" has ranked India 120th amongst 178 countries (The Times of India, 2008)) while China ranked at 83 and Pakistan at 76th. Economic freedom is very important to attract private investors in the Indian economy. Economic freedom is defined as the extent to which economic activity can be pursued without interference from government. This index was prepared by the Nobel laureate, Milton Friedman under the leadership of Fraser Institute, based in Canada in 1974. It is easier for investors to look at smaller countries or other emerging economies, where less than five procedures are needed to start a business compared to India's 13. High growth in real terms can be achieved and sustained only if red-tap is cut dramatically. It will allow business freedom to operate. Globalisation is a

consequence of deliberate efforts of western liberal countries to bring the whole world under one market oriented economic order. Observers point out those big multinational companies had always wanted to have free access to all markets in the world. The corporations are still hungry for profit, but emerging global norms do not allow them to use the kind of plundering strategy they earlier employed. Globalisation is bringing in new ideas for how to organise and how to govern the market. Therefore, when crafting policy, it is best to recognise the features of the world that we must take as given, and try to do our best subject to those constraints (Sinha, 2001). Accordingly, if poor nations can accept globalisation with a matured outlook, and adopt it on their terms with the interest of common people uppermost in their mind, like we Indian have done, there is no reason why globalisation cannot make this world a much better place to live in.

Impact of Globalisation

Globalisation is supposed to expose domestic industries to international competition. The intensity of impact of globalisation on industrial economy of India can be known with the help of classification of India's industrial economy. The classification of India's industrial economy is given below diagram.

Traditional industries are generally artisan-based (Prasad, 2005), located mostly in rural and semi-urban areas. These industries use local skills and resources and sell their products. These cottage industries involve lower levels of investment in plant and machinery and provide huge employment. Modern small-scale industries including 'tiny' units and power looms use power-driven machines and possess some technological sophistication (Sury, 2001). The lower volume of capital investment with higher potential of employment in small-scale industrial units provides them an edge over medium and large-scale industrial units. However, the plight of the contradiction is that the lower volume of capital investment required for the establishment of small-scale industrial units (SSI) attracts large number of investors and entrepreneurs to step into; but it also deprives such units from availing the benefits of *economy of size* and thus it results into weakening of their competitive position in the product and service markets as against the medium and large sized industrial giants (Singh, A.P. and Singh, V.P., 2009). This is why these small industries are not able to face the competition thrown by globalisation. Hence, the people employed in these industries are getting unemployed and are becoming poorer and their living standards are going lower than ever. This not only disturbs the socio-economic condition but also create social unrest in the society. The solution of contemporary crisis of unemployment

lies very much in the growth and development of SSIs. Under new global economic order they are facing twin problems to their survival. First, the requirement of small capital investment in SSI units is a blessing on one hand for their establishment and also a curse for their growth and development. Second, they are facing serious threat from the multinational corporations. Moreover, the SSI units generally fail to generate required quantum of borrowed capital from outside resources for the purpose of their growth and development only because of the reason that the small size of owned capital base does not generate confidence (as to protection of their funds) in the suppliers of long capital. Thus, the bankers, financial institutions and other suppliers of long term finance show reluctance in granting term loans to the SSI units. The resource ingredients for development of and industrial units are – Men, Machine, Material, Money, Market and Management (Singh, A.P. and Singh, V.P., 2009). The SSIs are generally clustered around one of these resource ingredients. They fulfil the requirement of local area. To tap such demand SSI units are developed in and around such market places. Management of SSI units are generally carried out by the owner-cum-manager, hence it does not, generally get the benefits of professionally trained managerial capabilities. Therefore, government must help them to avail the facilities of technology and credit facility to make them survive in the era of globalisation.

The rapid acceleration of growth has led to income inequality in India. Inequality in India is inter-state equality, closely followed by regional inequality within states, such as in the backward areas of fast growing states like Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. Regional inequality has persisted and increased due to a range of factors, including: higher initial endowments relating to health, education, agricultural potential, and infrastructure, agglomeration factors, urbanisation, income inequality, (Heady, 2010), lower government expenditure and higher government expenditure on the ‘development’ sector (Datt and Ravallion, 1998; Fan et al., 2000). Whatever the reasons for divergence in state growth rates, the sectoral sources of this divergence give an important insight into the proximate causes of rising inequality in India (Rao et al., 1999). The rising interstate inequality is generally deemed to have coincided with a period of substantial reform in India, beginning in 1990s. The reform process initiated in 1991 under the chairmanship of Narsimham (Pal, 2009) created different opportunities for different regions. Cities and states with existing advantages in manufacturing and high-tech services responded favourably, and the growth of these areas has increasingly

being supported by their state and municipal governments. But little has changed (Heady, 2010) in India's less developed regions in terms of either policy reforms or trend growth rates.

Epilogue

Globalisation per se is not a problem; in fact it is bringing opportunities for learning about organisation, coordination and management of available human capital, scarce resources and technology to increase production and productivity. Besides economic advantage it also helps to do away with long inherited social problems i.e., castes, superstition, parochial attitude etc. We need to understand the new emerging India. When an India of opportunities under the era of globalisation seems to be round the corner, it is futile to complain of globalisation. We must utilise our available resources and technology to take advantage of globalisation.

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